

Impact of Waste Water Irrigation around Hubli-Dharwad Region

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Abstract:

Urban environment represents a highly complex structure with greatly diversified secondary and tertiary activities and also with highly dense population. Industrialization and urbanization has provide livelihood and opportunity to millions in urban centers. However, these have also brought in its wake problems of waste generation, disposal contamination of environment air, soil, surface water, ground water etc., which have resulted in contamination hazard imperling human beings, live stock and plant life. The present paper highlights the waste water irrigation around the twin city region with its impact on farmers, plant positioning and soil clogging within the twin city of Hubli-Dharwad, Karnataka state. In the study region approximately 78 millions liters of wastewater is generated every day which flows untreated from sewers and wastewater nallas into the natural water courses that flows into the city's hinterland. This wastewater is an extremely valuable resources for urban peri-urban farmers and many extract it from the nallas and underground sewer pipes to irrigate their crops.

Introduction:

A healthy environment is the one which permits the highest quality of life with minimum of environmental problems. These environmental problems are the result of rapid population growth, urbanization, industrialization and modernization. Industrialization and urbanization has provided a livelihood and opportunities to millions in urban centers. However, these also brought in its wake problem of waste generation, disposal, contamination of environment air, soil, surface and ground water etc., which have resulted in contamination hazard imperilling human beings, live stock and plant live. One of the major sources of environmental problems is the waste generation which includes both soil and liquid waste. Liquid waste is wastewater which is discharged by the activities of people and drained out through municipal drains in many cases a river, tank or lake. The present paper highlights the wastewater irrigation around the city region. It also examines the impact of wastewater irrigation on farmers, plants poisoning and soil clogging in study area.

Hubli-Dharwad is the second largest urban agglomeration in Karnataka after Bangalore, the state capital in south-west India. Hubli and Dharwad were brought together under the Hubli-Dharwad municipal corporation in 1962. Today the bustling

university city is a pivotal transport hub and home to 800,000 people Hubli, the larger of the two is a regional centre for commerce, trade and industry, while Dharwad, located twenty two kilometres away is the administrative centre and host to several prestigious educational institutions. The city has rapidly expanding information technology sector alongside well established commerce & service sectors, but despite this the traditional practice of agriculture in and around the city remains strong and continues to play an important social and economic role. The climate of Hubli-Dharwad semi is arid and the rainfall across the peri-urban area varies, exceeding 1000 mm to the west of Dharwad and less than 700 mm to the east, the mean annual rainfall is 740 mm. In 1993 the % share of households connected to water, sewerage, electricity and telephone were 38%, 37%, 74% and 8% respectively. The households that are not connected to the piped water mains are dependent on either communal water taps or privately owned boreholes. Within the twin city approximately 78million liters of wastewater is generated per day. This flows, untreated via sewers and wastewater nallas (open drains) into natural water sources that flow into the hinterland. The details of drains and natural channels are given in the following table.

Table: Drains and Natural channels in Twin cities

Drain type	Length (in Kms)
Open drains (Pucca)	310
Open drains (Katcha)	12
Closed drains	5
Total drains	327
Natural channels	40

Source: City Municipal Corporation, Hubli-Dharwad 2008

In Dharwad, the main wastewater nalla flows to Madihal, once an outlying village but now incorporated as a suburb due to the expansion of the city. From the Madihal the nalla generally flows east passing in peripheries of Govankoppa, Gangadikoppa and Maradagi villages. In Hubli, the

main wastewater nalla flows to Bidnal, which is also now incorporated as a suburb. From Bidnal, the nalla generally flows south passing on the village peripheries of Gabbur, Budarsingi and Katnur. In both Hubli and Dharwad smaller pockets of wastewater irrigation can also be observed in the

other areas of the city, however the main area of wastewater irrigated agriculture are to be found along the two main nallas.

While collecting data total of 25 farmers were interviewed, consisting primarily of small holders with plot sizes below one hectare. In peri-urban areas of Hubli-Dharwad, land ownership and occupation are the principle criteria used by the villagers to describe characteristics of the poor. Indeed, many of the villagers themselves classify smallholders with plot sizes below two hectares as 'poor', while the landless often employed as agricultural labourers are classified as the very poor. The interviews were supported with cropping calendars and transect walks with the farmers through the areas that were irrigated with waste water.

Wastewater irrigated agriculture Main cropping pattern:

Along the main Dharwad and Hubli wastewater nallas three district cropping systems are apparent; vegetable production, field crops with vegetables and agro forestry (see table 2). The spatial variations of the cropping systems results from a combination of factors which include labour availability, farm size, market access, village conformity and soil types, with overriding aspect being the availability of wastewater itself. In the city and suburbs, where the wastewater supply is guaranteed, intensive vegetable production occurs. In locations where the supply is erratic and unreliable field crops and agro forestry predominate.

Table 2. Spatial Variation of wastewater irrigation cropping systems

Main nallas	Village	Distance (km)	Cropping system
Dharwad	Madihal	2.0	Vegetable production
	Govankoppa	5.4	Field crops & vegetables
	Gongadikoppa	9.2	Field crops & vegetables
	Maradagi	11.85	Field crops & vegetables
Hubli	Bidnal	2.5	Vegetables production
	Gabbur	8.9	Field crops & vegetables
	Budarsingi	10.7	Agro forestry
	Katnur	13.5	Agro forestry

Note: Distance – length of the waste nalla from city source to village including any meander.

Irrigation methods:

Regardless of the cropping systems used, the wastewater irrigation methods utilized along nallas remains same; consisting of an overland flow and furrow irrigation system using centrifugal pumps powered by either diesel motor or grid electricity. Wastewater is lifted from the nallas by means of the pump and delivered under pressure to the highest field elevation. From the outlet point the wastewater flows under gravity along the furrows

irrigating the crops. The opening and closing of the furrow is a precisely firmed operation to ensure soils are not left waterlogged and ridges are not inundated. However, the use of ridge and furrow irrigation (rather than flood irrigation) does not reduce the risk of crop contamination or reduce farmer exposure to wastewater. Despite this study being inconclusive due to the small sample size and the lack of a control it did highlight some of the health implications of wastewater irrigation.

The frequency of irrigation is dependent on the crop type, soil type and rainfall amount, with irrigation increasing in the dry season and during erratic rainfall conditions. Despite using a common irrigation method, one aspect, which remains heterogeneous, is that of wastewater filtration. Most farmers have adopted some method of filtering the wastewater as it is pumped from the nalla. The filtration serves two purposes; it prevents debris entering the pump hereby reducing wear and tear and it prevents the pooling of soils with any debris and solid wastes present in the waste water.

Risks presented by bio-medical waste

The results showed that crop samples taken from a ridge were still bacterially contaminated by the wastewater flowing in the furrow. Furthermore farmer exposure to wastewater during transplanting and weeding operations was increased as farmers stand in the flowing untreated waste water furrows. Indeed the effects of waste water on the health of 40 farmers from Madihal (Dharwad) and Gabbur village (Hubli) anaemia was identified as the commonest finding and was related to nutritional deficiency and to worm infestation. Most farmers have adopted some method for filtering the wastewater as it is pumped from the wastewater nallas. The rudimentary filtration is used to prevent soils becoming clogged with plastics, disposable syringes and other debris. Several farmers along both the nallas reported the presence of disposable needles and syringes in the wastewater, with one farmer having seen an intravenous giving set in the nalla. In Govankoppa a farmer complained of standing on needles buried in the soil upto 20 times in a single day. The foremost concern for these farmers is the cost of any medical treatment that is required if infection does occur. In Katnur, a farmer displayed a disposal syringe and needle that had been recovered from the filter fitted to the wastewater inlet pipe. In addition to raising regulatory issues regarding bio-medical waste control, these examples highlight the importance of farmers taking action themselves. The fitting of rudimentary filters to the wastewater inlets is crucial to mitigate the spread of disposable needles, debris and plastics into farmer's field.

Gender implications of wastewater irrigation

Regardless of the cropping system being used, the high nutrient loading from wastewater greatly increases the incidence of weeds; as already mentioned, farmers also attribute this to seeds that are carried in the wastewater and then pumped onto the fields. Consequently, as the main weed control method is hand tillage, the weeding accounts for the high labour inputs associated with wastewater irrigated cropping systems. Household members meet these inputs and within the household women normally carry out these tasks, likewise, when farm labourers are hired they are most likely to be women

due to the cheaper labour costs. Census data also confirms that a higher proportion of women are engaged in urban agriculture. The male population mainly seized the non-farm opportunities, as the wages are higher than in the agricultural sector. As well as perpetuating their positions as the poorest social group, their exposure to hazards of wastewater pathogens and organophosphate pesticide residues is also increased as they spend full days working on the fields. Furthermore, once the day's work is finished the women return to their households and carry out evening chores, including food preparation and cooking, thereby increasing the risk of pathogen transfer to other family members if basic hygienic standards are not maintained.

Risk reduction in livelihood strategies

There are wide variations in how plants and animals absorb, retain and transmit pathogens. With careful crop selection food chains can be designed to reduce the transmission of pathogens and other pollutants. The adoption of agro forestry systems reduces farmers direct contact with and exposure to wastewater, due to the reduced irrigation requirements of tree crops in comparison to vegetable crops. Poor farmers dependent on agriculture for their livelihood will always mitigate what they potentially perceive as risks and changing cropping systems is perceived as a high-risk strategy.

Conclusion:

The situation in Hubli-Dharwad highlights the failures of political policies and rather than that of bad farming practices. Diverse actors mould the wastewater irrigation farming systems that are located in the peri-urban areas, illustrating the contested political nature of urban and peri-urban agriculture. Firstly, the Hubli-Dharwad Municipal Corporation fails in its legal requirement to treat the discharged wastewater and are unlikely to implement such a programme in the near future on the grounds of cost. Wastewater treatment plants would certainly mitigate the public health and environmental risks that are associated with the wastewater nallas. Secondly, the actual moulding of wastewater irrigated agriculture has been hugely influenced by pesticide dealers; this has resulted in farmers becoming completely dependent on local pesticide dealers for their biased agriculture advice, which is inevitably linked to pesticide sales rather than that of good farming practices.

The outright banning of wastewater irrigation would be both unpractical and infeasible; in addition, for urban and peri-urban farmers the poverty implication of such a measure would be vast. Anyway, as noted in section 1.2 of the Hyderabad Declaration on wastewater use in irrigated agricultural; "with proper management, wastewater use contributes significantly sustaining livelihoods, food security and the quality of the

environment” (IWMI and IDRC, 2002:4). Therefore, the attainment of a ‘proper management’ approach is vital if the public health and environment risks are to be mitigated without threatening the livelihoods of marginalized farmers; the key to such an approach lies in education.

In Hubli-Dharwad, centralized or decentralized wastewater treatment plants are unlikely to be implemented in the near future, therefore, farmers irrigating with wastewater should be encouraged and supported to adopt safer and more sustainable farming practices. However the change from the current reliance on organophosphate pesticides to IPM (Integrated Pest Management) strategies, and the conversion to agro forestry practices will require long-term support through participatory approaches such as the use of farmer field schools that empower farmers through education and training in sustainable agricultural practices. The particular nature of the farming systems along the Dharwad and Hubli nallas and the complex nature of IPM suggest a village – based extension approach is likely to be the most suitable. The public health benefits of such an approach could also be enhanced through public education, aimed at raising awareness in disease prevention through better food handling, preparation and cooking practices.

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